

On War, Peace, and Infinitesimal Calculus

Only by taking an infinitesimally small unit for observation (the differential of history, that is, the individual tendencies of men) and attaining to the art of integrating them (that is, finding the sum of these infinitesimals) can we hope to arrive at the laws of history.

(Leo Tolstoy, *War and Peace*)

Abstract

Attempts to see reality as being inherently in conflict and in motion rather than at rest have a famous unsettling quality; namely, of treating conflict and motion as something at rest. This is what happened to Engels' 'dialectical laws' in his *Anti-Dühring*—allegedly an elaboration of what he and Marx referred to as their 'old Hegel' and their logical reconstruction of *infinitesimal calculus*. I will demonstrate how the 'old Hegel', in fact, differs from such opinions, arguing that conflict and motion are not an opposition of objects at rest, but something contained within, or belonging to, their form. This also resolves the initial paradox.

Key words

Infinitesimal calculus; Becoming; Relation; Speculative Logic; Hegel; Clausewitz; dialectical laws; bad infinity; Engels.

In Tolstoy's *War and Peace* (Tolstoy 2010: 882), there is a scene in which general von Clausewitz, who, like many other Prussians, entered Russian service during the campaign against Napoleon, appears on horseback and takes part in the following conversation: '*Der Krieg muss in Raum verlegt werden*', he says, since '*der Zweck ist nur den Feind zu schwächen, so kann man gewiss nicht den Verlust der Privat-Personen in Achtung nehmen*' (Tolstoy 2010: 830).¹

Prince Andrei, who overhears this, is irritated because this extended 'Raum' is where his father

¹ 'The war must be extended widely', since 'the only aim is to weaken the enemy, so of course one cannot take into account the loss of private individuals'.

and sister live, while the generals ‘have nothing in their German heads but theories not worth an empty egg-shell (Tolstoy 2010: 830–831).

This scene, like many others in the novel, reflects Tolstoy’s very own philosophy of history, where Germans are described as ‘military theorists who believed in a science of war with immutable laws—laws of oblique movements, outflankings, and so forth’ (Tolstoy 2010: 680). By contrast, the Russians respect the concrete situations and people in their individuality, as witnessed by Kutuzov’s ‘irrational’ decisions, such as losing the Battle of Borodino (thereby exhausting Napoleon’s army) and retreating (far enough to allow Napoleon to take Moscow and become stranded there without supplies). It results in the famous analogy between the laws of history and those of calculus, based on the tendencies of individual men and not *vice versa*.

I find this analogy instructive because it presents calculus as an alternative model of the world in motion and perpetual war, rather than in repose and peace. Such a sentiment is by no means exclusive to Tolstoy. It is echoed influentially in Engels’ *Dialectics of Nature* (Engels 2010), with calculus extended from the laws of history to the laws of nature:

The differential calculus for the first time makes it possible for natural science to represent mathematically *processes* and not only *states*: motion. (Engels 2010: 550)

As such, it is an example of general dialectics—or ‘the science of the most general laws of *all* motion’ (Engels 2010: 545)—which provides a solution to the dilemma of theory versus life.

In my paper, I would like to look at this dilemma as misconceived by means of the calculus itself, with reference to the source of dialectical thinking: Hegel’s *Science of Logic*,² which

² Abbreviations used:

PR = Hegel, *Outlines of the Philosophy of Right*, trans. T. M. Knox (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008).

PS = Hegel, *The Phenomenology of Spirit*, trans. T. Pinkard (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018).

SL = Hegel, *The Science of Logic*, trans. G. di Giovanni (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010)/WA: 5.

EP = Hegel, *Encyclopedia of the Philosophical Sciences in Basic Outline. Part I: Science of Logic*, trans. K. Brinkmann and D. Dahlstrom (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press 2010).

WA = Hegel, *Werkausgabe* (Frankfurt: Suhrkamp 1969).

systematically uses calculus to achieve goals at variance with the ideas of Marx and Engels. The main idea is that motion or war are not in opposition to theory and peace, as a truer kind of reality, but are rather part of them. This is also, as I will conclude, what Clausewitz understood, but Tolstoy obviously did not, which makes the former a true representative of modernity.

I. The World in Motion

While Tolstoy was mainly interested in calculus as part of a mathematical education—and had no interest in Hegel at all—Marx and Engels were enthusiastic about both, to the extent that the editors of Marx’s estate were able to collect an entire volume containing his mathematical writings, which are mostly his notes on how calculus works. Engels, as usual, was enthusiastic about Marx being enthusiastic, incorporating calculus into his *Dialectics of Nature*:

The turning point in mathematics was Descartes’ *variable magnitude*. With that came *motion* and hence *dialectics* in mathematics, and *at once, too, of necessity the differential and integral calculus*, which moreover immediately begins, and which on the whole was completed by Newton and Leibniz, not discovered by them. (Engels 2010: 537)

Obviously, the link between calculus and motion is not of Engels’ own invention. Newton himself developed it from his interest in physics, using the vocabulary of ‘fluents’, ‘fluxions’, and ‘flowing quantities’ as an explanatory tool. Still, the aim of calculus was simply to quantify the circumferences, areas, and volumes of complicated, ‘curved’ shapes—such as the orbits of planets—by transforming them into simpler, ‘rectangular’ ones.

Figure 1

Ancient mathematics already knew this, treating the circle as a polygon with very small—perhaps infinitely so—sides, but calculus brought a systematic approach to the matter by

reducing the multiple cases to two complementary ones: differentiation and integration. See Figure 1.

The idea behind them is as follows: *Differentiation* is to measure the slope of the tangent t to the given curve k at the point P by ‘taking the difference’ in a small neighbourhood of P , expressing it as the ratio of very small differences Δy and Δx . These are the sides of the so-called *characteristic triangle* PQR —which is not a triangle at all—and ‘roughly’ corresponds to the triangle ABP . Since the smaller the ‘triangle’ the better the ratio captures the slope of the tangent, the idea arises that the best approximation is when the differences Δx and Δy are as small as possible, symbolically dx and dy . In view of this, they should be both

- (1) *finite*, since otherwise they cannot form a difference dy/dx , yielding a nonsensical expression of $0/0$, and
- (2) *less than any finite quantity*, since otherwise a better approximation would be possible.

A similar consideration applies to *integration*, where the area under the curve k bounded by the x -axis is calculated. Here, the area is divided into a finite number of rectangles, with the same observation that the smaller the rectangle the better the approximation, concluding that it must be best when the rectangles are *infinitesimally small*.

II. Engels the Mathematician

The crucial logical question now is not so much how one can sum an infinite number of infinitely small quantities, but rather, in what sense they are *quantities* at all. Newton’s answer is infamously vague, operating with the *transient state* in which the quantum finds itself just before disappearing.³ This means treating infinitesimals as both *still existing* and *soon to be no more*, justified in this contradictory conflicting quality by the very nature of motion.

³ See (Newton 1962: 39): ‘[...] by the ultimate velocity is meant that with which the body is moved, neither before it arrives at its place and the motion ceases, not after, but at the very instant it arrives; that is the velocity with which the body arrives at its last place, and with which the motion ceases. And in like manner, by the ultimate ratio of evanescent quantities is to be understood the ratio of the quantities not

Enchanted by anything in motion and in conflict, Engels adopted this idea as not only a sufficient basis for calculus, but also for a new logic,⁴ phrasing both as follows (my bold type):

[1] First, I differentiate x and y , i.e., I take x and y as so infinitely small that in comparison with any real quantity, however small, **they disappear** [...] In place of x and y ; therefore, I have **their negation**, dx and dy , in the formulas or equations before me.

[2] I continue then to operate with these formulas, treating dx and dy as quantities which are **real**, though subject to certain exceptional laws, and at a certain point **I negate the negation**, i.e., I integrate the differential formula, and in place of dx and dy again get the real quantities x and y , and **am then not where I was at the beginning** [...]. (Engels 2010: 127–128.)

What we have here, applied to calculus, is the *law of double negation*, as articulated in *Anti-Dühring* together with other dialectical laws such as the transformation of quantity into quality. As the quote itself indicates, Engels feels very confident and nonchalant about these, ridiculing mathematicians who became dialecticians against their own will and referring to ‘the old Hegel’, who is usually ‘quite right’, even on matters of calculus. (Marx 1983: XVII.)

What is striking is that ‘the old’ Hegel thought otherwise, and explicitly so, in both *mathematics and logic*. And this *is not* because he did not think of the world in terms of motion and conflict, but because he treated them as having a specific *structure* that could not be reduced to mere positive words—which is an attitude he criticized as *formalism*. A quick insight into what is meant can be gained from the logical fallacy he highlighted as the problem of ‘bad infinity’.

before they vanish, not afterwards, but with which they vanish. In like manner the first ratio of nascent quantities is that with which they begin to be’.

⁴ As for the contradiction, Engels (2010: 112), makes the following observation: ‘We have already noted that one of the basic principles of higher mathematics is the contradiction that in certain circumstances straight lines and curves may be the same. [...] But even lower mathematics teems with contradictions. It is for example a contradiction that a root of A should be a power of A , and yet $A^{1/2} = \sqrt{A}$. It is a contradiction that a negative quantity should be the square of anything, for every negative quantity multiplied by itself gives a positive square’.

First, consider the *quantum* as something *determinate*, or *finite*, as Hegel would call it, and notice that this finiteness can easily be violated when our concepts, intentions, or theories encounter the real world, which is, so to speak, ‘measured’ by them. Then:

The infinitely small signifies in the first instance the negation of the quantum as such, that is, of the so-called *finite* expression, of the completed determinateness that quantum as such possesses. (SL: 258/355.)

Second, consider that it is one thing to say (1) that this quantum is not finite, this concept is not sharp, or this justice is not perfect, and another thing entirely (2) to let these negations represent a new quality—an *infinite* quantum, concept, or justice, probably found somewhere beyond our world—and even more, (3) to claim that this is because the world is in motion and a new logic is needed to correctly describe this peculiarity. Fuzzy logic, for example, wrongly conceived as the true logic of this world, is an example of the same illusion.

III. Being and Becoming

It is for a variety of these interconnected, conceptual reasons that the calculus appears at the beginning of the *Science of Logic*, as part of Hegel’s analysis of the categories of *Being (Sein)*—standing for Repose—and *Becoming (Werden)*—standing for Motion—, as well as the first justification of the core of the dialectical method: the concept of Sublation (*Aufhebung*).

Figure 2

What Hegel does is recalibrate the opposition of Being and

Becoming, in accord with his idiosyncratic idea of Being contaminated by Negativity. He begins with the observation that saying that something ‘is’ in a pure, unqualified way is empty, amounting to saying that it ‘is not’, which he presents as the identity of Pure Being with Pure Nothing. Specific Being, or Being-Here, is never just positively present, but always *related to*

what it is not, or separated from it, by drawing a boundary. See Figure 2. This is what his motto, '*determinatio est negatio*', clearly represents.

It gives *Being-Here* an unstable quality, since the given boundary can always be, by definition, tampered with, leading us to a new boundary, and so on. *Becoming*, in this sense, is not an opposition to *Being*, but rather its *Form*, or the form of its instability. See Figure 3.

Grammatically speaking, one can follow Stekeler-Weithofer (2019: 142–143) here and read this

in terms of the German 'wird', along with all categories that resist the formalism of the indicative mood, and 'was', 'will be', 'would be', and so on. They all represent something transitory, differentiating more finely within what 'is' and 'is not', but they do not refer to a more real

Figure 3

fluctuating world of entities such as the infinitesimals; they build on it. And this is what Hegel explicitly says *pace* Newton (bold type mine):

These magnitudes are so determined that they *are in their vanishing*—not *before* this vanishing, for they would then be finite magnitudes; not *after* it, for then they would be nothing. Against this pure thought, it is objected and endlessly repeated that these magnitudes are ***either something or nothing***; that there is ***no intermediary state*** between being and nothing (“state” is here an inappropriate, barbaric expression). (SL: 79–80/110–111.)

Translated into *physical vocabulary*, it says something as follows: If some Object is capable of Motion, then that Object must be, in a sense, Immovable, otherwise, Motion would be meaningless. And this is what the idea of infinitesimals ignores by transforming Motion into the immovable Object itself. Calculus, then, as well as its new ‘dialectical logic’, represent a ‘style of reasoning which makes and clings to the false presupposition of the absolute separateness of being and non-being’ and, as such, ‘is to be named not dialectic but sophistry’ (SL: 80/111).

IV. The Path Is the Goal

After clarifying this point, we can still ask whether such a complicated device as infinitesimals was needed to show this. The answer is yes, by deepening a parallel between the structure of infinitesimals-talk, which arises from an approximative process, and the cognitive *process* as a series of negative delimitations. This leaves us with two extreme positions:

- (E1) One is general *skepticism*, which stems from the possibility of negating the given boundary indefinitely, so that no fixed result of knowledge can be obtained.
- (E2) The other is transcendent *escapism*, which posits a result in the transfinite beyond that our negations will eventually reach or at least get near to.

For Hegel, both these standpoints are conceptual traps— bad negations of each other—to be overcome by *immanent means*. A proper understanding of the calculus and its underlying concepts provides a complex model for doing so.

The basic guide here is Hegel's favourite example, the series 0.285714..., which—by having no determinate goal—is a case of bad conceptualization, or bad infinity. This can be remedied, though, by providing its 'ought', or the specific limit $2/7$ (SL: 211/289–290), which, as Hegel points out, is a ratio, or a *Relation*. The true extent of this reference is revealed in passages like this:

The series exhibits the contradiction inherent in it of representing something which is a **relation**, and possesses *qualitative* nature within it, as **without relation**, as a mere *quantum*, as amount. (SL: 210/288.)

I read it as follows: Infinitesimals are not independent objects, but rather *relations* of a given series to its limit, if one exists. Thus, when measuring curved space with a rectangular figure, I do not need transient entities to identify the former with the latter, for example, a characteristic 'triangle' with the real one. I merely relate these to each other.

Now, in view of the previous analysis, which eliminated infinitesimals as Being, this looks easy enough. But real insight emerges when this relational reading is generalized. The series 0.285714... is an example of something that we know from elementary school as the decimal expansion of a real number. But it is a very specific case, which adopts the rational number as a limit. For many, such as 3.141592..., there is no such limit, or ratio, available, which is why they are known as *irrational*. It is more than a matter of historical interest that the Greeks called them ‘alogoi logoi’, *irrational ratios*, thus suggesting that they are ratios after all but in a sense yet to be construed. And this is what Hegel’s analysis essentially aims at.

The basic idea was introduced by Georg Cantor, and therefore could not be known to Hegel, but it fully aligns with his requirement that a series ‘has the determination of infinity *within itself*’ (SL: 211/290). And this by providing the series with a limit by *relating* it not to something pre-given, but *to itself*. What Cantor did, in fact, was to take the sequence of rational numbers that was to identify some point on the real axis, and to say that *this point is this sequence itself*—though not just like that, but after it meets the property of ‘thickening’ over all measures. And this obtains when for any difference c —however small, yet finite and rational—there is a member of the series after which the distance between all the members is smaller than c .⁵

By making the series ‘convergent’ in this immanent sense by relating it to the inner property of ‘thickening’, the reals were finally introduced as numbers, two thousand years after incommensurability was discovered, as a kind of bad negation of the original theory of reals.

⁵ This is defined for any sequence of rational numbers, of which the decimal expansions are, in fact, specific, normalized cases that meet the ‘convergence’ or also the Cauchy condition almost by definition. This is due to their form, which, in the case of 3.141592..., simply represents the sequence of rational numbers 3, 31/10, 314/100, 3141/1000, 31415/10000, 314159/100000..., 3141592/1000000, ... In general, though, there are series that ‘diverge’, such as the seemingly convergent harmonic series $1 + 1/2 + 1/3 + 1/4 + \dots$, which is the abbreviation for the sequence 1, $1 + 1/2$, $1 + 1/2 + 1/3$, $1 + 1/2 + 1/3 + 1/4$, ...

V. $X = X + Y$

Approximation as a self-reflexive relation led us, by analogy, to the idea of knowledge as a process that directs us to its result by becoming that result itself. It is, in the end, a way to avoid the cliffs (E1) and (E2), representing a *process without a result*, and a *result without a process*.

In order not to become too abstract, simply think here first of everyday experience, such as *household chores*, which children hate and try to avoid because they see them through the following partial truth: the moment one finishes cleaning, the mess is already there again, thus there is no point to it in the sense of no *fixed result*. In adopting this, Hegel claims, children are a kind of formal logician (*EP: §80*),⁶ sticking to perpetual Being, which makes them skeptical later when they leave the stability of home and become the dialecticians of perpetual Becoming. The secret of chores is that they are conceived as both process and result. Besides the quality of *eternal suffering*, they also have the quality of *work done*, bringing Being and Becoming together.

And this is how the analysis by means of Relation deepens our insight into the negativity of Being. As we said, some Being X never arises directly, but by separation from what it is not, within the original Pure Being, or, recursively, within the network of the separations made up so far, which Hegel calls Concept. The immanent point

emphasizes that these separations cannot be made *from the outside*, as the cliffs (E1) and (E2) suggest, but *from within*, which redraws the underlying picture as follows: Rather than separating X from Y from the external point Z, one must perform this operation from the original point of X itself, arriving at its separation into the proper part X and its

Figure 4

negation Y. See Figure 4. As a relation of X to X itself, this leads us to the equation $X = X + Y$. The following remarks are an elaboration of this:

⁶ 'It is the way of youth to relish abstractions, whereas a person with the experience of life does not indulge in the abstract *either-or*, clinging instead to what is concrete'.

(1) Primarily, this relation obtains between the original X and its correction by Y . Becoming, then, is the form of knowledge, expressed in the equation $X = X + Y$, and the Being is the *immovable* value of the given variable.

(2) Thus, and contrary to (E1), knowledge is possible, but not as corresponding to the pre-given world, as (E2) claims, but to our attempts at it once they are recognized *as failures*. These failures— positively taken, in their relation to knowledge that corrected them—make knowledge stable enough to be considered an improvement, in the sense of Peirce, rather than of Popper and their seemingly shared concept of verisimilitude.

(3) Such an improvement cannot be measured externally but instead by the entire structure's 'thickening', in both a diachronic and synchronic manner, which is *hermeneutic* all the way down. This because one always arrives at the same point X , or the original being that is thickened, enriched by the experience of the journey Y . See Figure 5.

Figure 5

Hegel's anthropological similes substantially help here when presenting the whole picture, or 'Absolute', in terms of an old man who perceives the *same* differences he started with as a child *differently*, from the perspective of his whole life. (*EP*: §230.)⁷ This corrects the ontological standpoint of youth (and the dialectical standpoint of adulthood) by a speculative attitude, in which, so to speak, the form of $X = X + Y$ becomes identical with its content.

VI. The Grammar of War

With all this in mind, let us revisit the initial dilemma, phrased as an *expressive problem* of talking about *transient* phenomena, such as war, motion, and life, in a *static* manner. If we focus

⁷ 'In this respect, the absolute idea is comparable to the old man who says the same religious sentences as the child does, but for the old man they have the meaning of his entire life. Even if the child understands the religious content, what validity that content has for him is still of the sort that lies outside his entire life and world'.

on the negativity involved, we can link it to everyday situations, such as when progressive teachers persuade children that it is okay to make mistakes, having probably just harmless things in mind, such as failing a math test, rather than setting the school on fire. The problem, then, is how to describe negative phenomena without approving of them as something worth doing. Hegel is often accused of doing just that when claiming, for example, that war unites a state (*PS*: §324) or that fearing error is the biggest error one can commit (*PS*: §74, 50).

The given logical analysis provided a kind of resolution here: When discussing war, conflict, or mistakes, we are not referring to something incompatible with Being—in the exclusive sense of Either-Or—, but to something that is part of Being, as its Form, which is Becoming. The equation $X = X + Y$ was to capture this through its relational form, which resists mere positive reading without abandoning it entirely. And this consists in construing relationality not from an *absolute point* outside but from one of the *related parts*—that is, *self-reflexively*.

Tolstoy's problem with Clausewitz, with which my exposition began, lay in Tolstoy's overlooking or rather purposefully ignoring the fact that Clausewitz was interested in such a stratified effort, conceiving of war not as a matter of static laws, which he explicitly criticizes as a 'mathematical theory' (Clausewitz 1989: 178), but as filled with unpredictable parameters, in terms of the 'fog of war' (Clausewitz 1989: 101) or the 'frictions' (Clausewitz 1989: 119) it is accompanied by. This led him to grasp war as a 'continuation of political discourse' rather than an *absolute* phenomenon.⁸ Let me quote:

We maintain [...] that war is simply a continuation of political intercourse, with the addition of other means. We deliberately use the phrase "with the addition of other means" because we also want to make it clear that war in itself does not suspend

⁸ The term 'absolute war', which Clausewitz famously uses, is arguably not meant in opposition to politically conditioned warfare, but rather to war with a 'limited aim', in which the goal is to prevent the enemy from continuing the fight rather than to destroy his military power entirely. In the given sense, the absolute concept of war is that of the 'ideal war' which, according to Clausewitz, is a purely logical construct that ignores existing political constraints and aspects of human nature. (Clausewitz 1989: 88.)

political intercourse or change it into something entirely different. [...] How could it be otherwise? Do political relations between peoples and between their governments stop when diplomatic notes are no longer exchanged? Is war not just another expression of their thoughts, another form of speech or writing? Its grammar, indeed, may be its own, but not its logic. (Clausewitz 1989: 605.)

Now, turn your attention to the last sentence, which arguably states that *war has its own grammar, but no logic*. This offers a very apt summary of our problem in the following sense: War's grammar is part of everything that exists, without being something simply existing or desirable, which is what the equation $X = X + Y$ expresses in its generality. As a mere formula, however, it requires not only a semantic understanding, but also a kind of achievement. And this consists of reading it precisely in a *self-reflexive* way, applying negativity or relationality to itself. Otherwise, one will fall into the same trap as Engels did with calculus and dialectical laws by mistaking, so to speak, one's grammar for one's logic.

Here, logic means the same as what Hegel calls *formality*: an *alienated attitude* observed, for example, in those who preach the instability, vanity, and insecurity of temporal things. Yet, 'if this insecurity now actually comes on the scene in all seriousness in the form of hussars with shining sabers, then the moving and edifying discourses which foretold all these events turn into curses against the invader'. (PR: §324.) With this, the proper part of my argument ends.

Additional Remarks

This argument, inevitably, has many gaps to be bridged and details to be filled. At the same time, the exposition must remain concise, since—as Hegel well understood—details can easily be tampered with once the entire structure has been thought through. The connection between these details and the structure is ultimately held together by a stimulating *example*.

While the phenomenon of infinitesimals may not be such an example itself, at least it points to one: to the concept of real magnitude as something complex enough to make all the logical

aspects of interest clearly visible. As such, it is a significant contribution to intellectual history, rather than a mere episode in the history of science. Let me quickly review and expand on this:

(1) First, the concept of *Negation* is introduced in its bad form of a *mere refutation* of the hypothesis of commensurability, to be reconciled later within the concept of the real number as a kind of second, determining negation. This development gives rise to the notion of *Sublation*, according to which a contradiction that has been removed remains visible, as is exemplified by the concept of *alogoi logoi*.⁹

(2) Second, the concept of *Infinity* emerges when incommensurability is treated as an *infinite process* of measuring rather than a mere failure to produce a finite result. This keeps the negativity sublated by a rule; for example, the rule that allows us to develop the series 3.141592..., which corresponds to the ratio of a circle's circumference to its diameter.

(3) Third, the concept of the *Whole* is reconstructed based on the totality of reals and their *Closure*. This is what Hegel's idea of the *Absolute* offers: the conceptual whole or the Concept in its stabilized, 'good' form. Paradoxes of infinity easily transgress such a totality by, for example, finding a bigger set to the 'biggest one there is', which stems precisely from the 'bad' form of the Concept, closed in a rigid, finite sense. Cantor's idea of *non-denumerability* helps here to elaborate on the notion of the 'right' closure that keeps the totality open.¹⁰

Together, all these *logical aspects*, as applied to the concept of a real number, provide for the concept of Being that is (1) based on negativity, which is its *ontological determination*; (2) is procedural by nature, which is its *dialectical form*; and (3) is holistic all the way down, which belongs to its *speculative form*.¹¹ As Concept, this Being is developed and closed both diachronically and synchronically, becoming an *Idea*, or the Concept in its projective Relation to

⁹ See my book ...

¹⁰ For an elaboration on this idea, see my paper ...

¹¹ For a detailed comment on the significance of Hegel's logical hierarchy, see my paper ...

the World. The *Absolute Idea* is the Concept that is closed self-reflexively, so that the Relation becomes a Self-Relation.

In all these layers, Becoming stands for the relationality of Being, beginning with (1) its delimitation to what it *is not*, or synchronically, and with (2) its delimitation to what it is *no longer*, or diachronically. The latter approach leads to the historical concept of truth, which is rooted in correcting previous attempts at it that are now considered failures; not *per se*, but in relation to that correction. (3) Both delimitations add up to the relation of the whole of Being, or Concept, to itself, and to all the differences made so far. Consequently, Becoming is a form of Being, expressed by the equation $X = X + Y$ rather than Being itself.

However, this does not preclude the possibility of turning Becoming into Being, or the Object of consideration, such as in the theory of war. This is because, as a relation of X to $X + Y$, Becoming becomes part of the new object as the trace of its history. One could also phrase it as follows: Studying Becoming requires more than viewing it as devoid of Being, of which it is a form, unless one risks destroying it by separating Process from Result, and *vice versa*. This possibility, on the other hand, is never *real*, only virtual, and consists of *an alienated attitude* toward Being, which is always a mixture of both.

This observation is an important exegetical point because we do not first have the imperfect states of knowledge, such as the skeptical or transcendent ones, in which the process and result—Being and Becoming—are separated, waiting for their sublation. Rather, the full form of knowledge is already there once we begin to know, and the missing or lost element is the proper attitude towards it, which renders these imperfect states as alienations of knowledge rather than its precursors, either synchronically or diachronically. This is also what the *hermeneutic circle* is meant to capture.

In this spirit, let me revisit Tolstoy's *War and Peace*, not as a theory of history and war, but as a profound exploration of human nature and its conflicting qualities coexisting together, so masterly and 'realistically' depicted in scenes like when the old Prince Bolkonsky teaches his

daughter, Princess Marya, geometry, filled with anger and pity at the same time: ‘without being a hardhearted man he inspired such fear and respect as few hard-hearted men would have aroused’. (Tolstoy 2010: 93.) This is precisely what Wittgenstein refers to when he notes that ‘when [Tolstoy] turns his back to the reader then he seems to me *most* impressive. [...] It seems to me his philosophy is most true when it is *latent* in the story’. (Malcolm 2001: pp. 142–143.)

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